

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *The article reveals the need to master the system of theoretical and artistic concepts, the foundations of realistic art, to perform creative tasks using life, memory, various visual materials in order to develop the creative competence of students.*

Keywords: *art, life, memory, image, thought, dictionary, directory.*

Introduction

Before going directly to the issue of developing creative competencies of schoolchildren, it is permissible to define the concept of creativity.

There are many definitions in psychology, philosophy and pedagogy. But they are united by one thing, that is, creativity - this is the change of the world and the person. Creativity is the driving force of human development. The following features are characteristic of a creative person: interest in complex and ambiguous things, tendency to ask questions, sudden interest, ability to solve the same problem for a long time.

Analysis of literature on the topic

T.V. Kudryavtsev analyzed the problems of creative activity in the educational process, and V.G. Razumovsky analyzed creative issues and problems [2, 3]. In this case, P.N. Andrianov shows the creative activity in the following stages on the example of students' technical creativity: perception and justification of the idea; technical development of the assignment; work on a task (object); testing the object at work and evaluating the result of the creative solution [1]. However, development of students' creative competencies is carried out through such creative tasks as mastering the system of theoretical and artistic concepts, the basics of realistic art, analysis of works of art from life, memory, description, describing, using various visual materials, critically evaluating one's feelings and thoughts, one's own and others' activities verbally and graphically, in various situations, referring to encyclopedias, dictionaries, reference books.

Research methodology

The following conditions are necessary for the development of creative competencies of schoolchildren:

- adoption of a humanitarian position by teachers and parents of students;
- recognition of equal partnership (teacher - children);
- the teacher's own initiative;
- studying the child as a valuable person;
- high level of communication with society and environment;
- mastered and acquired knowledge and skills - the basis of students' knowledge and creative activity;

- active approach based on taking into account and distinguishing the level of intellectual development of the student, as well as his preparation, ability and inclination in the field of education;

- using tasks of different levels of complexity;
- use of innovative technologies: information and communication, problem-based education, project activities, developmental and multi-level education;
- directing the educational process to the development of the student's independence and responsibility for the results of his activity;
- integration of basic and additional education.

We offer a methodological system consisting of the following main components for the development of students' creative competences:

1. Diagnosing and controlling the level of formation of students' creative competencies, skills and qualifications.

2. Targeted long-term planning of creative abilities, taking into account the qualitative growth of the personal achievements of each student and the prospects for the development of students' abilities according to the individual educational trajectory.

3. Creating psychological-pedagogical and organizational-technological conditions for the formation of creative competence of students through the use of innovative educational technologies, ways, methods and forms; designing the educational process through the system of classroom and extracurricular activities.

4. Correcting and planning further educational work based on the evaluation of the effectiveness of one's own pedagogical activities aimed at the formation and development of creative qualities of a person and the analysis and reflection of the results.

As a result of the created conditions, the following qualities of creative competence are formed in students:

- creativity, ability to solve problems, ingenuity;
- flexibility and criticality of mind, intuition, originality and self-confidence;
- the ability to set and solve non-standard tasks, the ability to analyze, synthesize and combine, the ability to transfer experience, the ability to foresee, etc.;

- emotional and volitional qualities: spirituality, emotional elevation in creative situations, associativeness, imagination, distraction, sense of novelty, sensitivity to contradictions, emotional ability;

- emptiness of thoughts, feelings and actions, perception, ability to overcome stereotypes;
- the ability to form hypotheses, hypotheses and prove them;
- self-organization, criticality, thinking- creativity, ability to solve problems, ingenuity;
- flexibility and criticality of mind, intuition, originality and self-confidence;
- the ability to set and solve non-standard tasks, the ability to analyze, synthesize and combine, the ability to transfer experience, the ability to foresee, etc.;

- emotional and volitional qualities: spirituality, emotional elevation in creative situations, associativeness, imagination, imagination, sense of novelty, sensitivity to contradictions, emotional ability;

- emptiness of thoughts, feelings and actions, perception, ability to overcome stereotypes;
- the ability to form hypotheses, assumptions and prove them;
- self-organization, criticality, thinking.

In the process of forming a child's personality, creativity goes through two stages of development:

The first, primary creativity is a general creative ability that is not specialized in a certain area of human life, it manifests itself in the form of imitation of adults (for the student - the teacher) as a creative example. The second stage is specialized creativity - creative ability is related to a certain field of activity. The result that shows the formation of creativity is the transition to original creativity. Any creativity is determined by environmental factors. A good memory and a high level of intelligence are indicators of the presence of creativity in the future. Creativity can be small and large: small - manifestation of non-standard creativity and manifestation of originality in everyday situations. Large creativity has a significant impact on culture and society as a whole. In an educational institution, the child goes through the first stage of creativity and develops small creativity. A systematic approach to the organization of the student's creative activity during the lesson creates conditions for the transition to large creativity.

Systematic monitoring, comparative analysis of educational achievements of schoolchildren allow to timely identify further measures to monitor the effectiveness of the learning and development process, eliminate the gaps in students' knowledge and develop their personal culture.

The result of the formation of students' creative abilities: the desire to create their own creative products in class and extracurricular activities, individual achievements of students in competitions and exhibitions, to perform creative work and apply the acquired knowledge.

The creative activity of students opens up great opportunities for educating and developing their personality, forming their creative abilities, and maintaining a constant interest in science. Analyzing the creative activity and work of students, it is necessary to achieve the following performance indicators for the formation of creative competence of schoolchildren:

- students should have the knowledge, skills, qualifications and system of personal qualities necessary for creativity, observation, creativity of thinking, initiative in creative activities;
- children's transition from passive acquisition of knowledge to active, creative application of it in new conditions, deeper and more conscious solving of various problems;
- the creative component is present in communicative, educational activities and is actively manifested in various forms of independent activity.

Students regularly and voluntarily perform various creative activities: they participate in contests, quizzes, publish newspapers, didactic and visual aids, multimedia projects, conduct research, prepare reports, participate in and win various contests and exhibitions on various level.

The use of modern information and communication technologies in the lesson gives students the opportunity to gain primary experience in the implementation of educational research and projects, to form the ability to present the results of their independent work, which are later used in the lesson. Children's performances and works are distinguished by the depth of research, correctness of conclusions and expressiveness of material presentation.

Research results

The purpose of the experiment on the development of creative competencies of schoolchildren can be defined as follows:

To contribute to the formation of a creative person who is ready to contribute to self-development, public culture, building a new society.

Objectives:

- to identify, take into account and develop students' creative abilities;
- to introduce schoolchildren to various creative activities with a specific product;
- to cultivate love and respect for the artist and his work.

Undoubtedly, the environment is one of the decisive factors in the formation and development of a creative person. At school, there is a reliable, creative partnership between teacher and pupils, which creates a collective spiritual life..

As a methodological basis for the formation of creative competences, it is possible to obtain a comprehensive system of principles, methods and training manuals from "L.V. Zankov's Development Program" and "N.E. Shurkova's Value Education Program". These programs have creative content because they are based on:

- 1) learning and mastering the main topics and human values;
- 2) combining topics and problems;
- 3) interdisciplinarity;
- 4) consideration of "open type" problems;
- 5) high level of content saturation.

The main idea behind these programs is personal attention. The principles and rules of the person-centered approach can be applied by considering creative competencies as an understanding of the individual's uniqueness:

- accepting a child as normal
- natural consistency of the educational process
- creation of humanitarian relations in the team
- assessment of the growth of a particular person.
- development of child's creativity through teacher's creativity
- evaluating the success of a pupil as the success of a teacher
- Accepting the Motherland as a subject of cultural creation (the Motherland is our unique gifts and talents).

Conclusions and suggestions

In order to develop students' creative competences, it is necessary to address their emotional reactions and situations first. When creating tasks, it is necessary to arouse the student's emotions such as joy, surprise, love, anger, even envy.

In addition, the following methods, ways and tools help in the development of creative competences:

- state of novelty, surprise, success and failure
- updating knowledge and skills
- use of visual, audiological and tactile information
- Use of ICT (presentations, videos, simulators)
- conversations-dialogues, discussions, analysis of life situations
- competitions, debates, games, theatrical performances.
- visiting the theater, exhibitions, museums, concerts, excursions.

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